

Error Estimation for Gridded Bathymetry¹

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Abstract

Estimating the uncertainty or predicted accuracy of gridded products that are generated from historical bathymetric survey data is of high interest to the maritime navigation community. Surface interpolation methods used for gridding survey data in practice are well established. This paper investigates error estimation methods for gridded bathymetry in terms of their practical utility. Of particular interest are: 1) assessing the quality of *a priori* uncertainty of random error in survey data; 2) the significance of autocorrelated random errors; 3) the relationship between survey point density and propagated or product uncertainty; 4) the computational feasibility of Monte Carlo (*MC*) methods over large regions; and 5) the value of cross-validation to estimate error in the absence of controlled truth. *K*-fold cross-validation is used as the basis for performance evaluation of our approach to propagate *a priori* random errors via *MC* perturbation with spline-in-tension surface interpolation. Experiments are conducted with test areas in the Norwegian archipelago of Svalbard.

Key words: error estimation; cross-validation; autocorrelation; Monte Carlo; spline-in-tension

1. Introduction

Bathymetric data remains sparse for large portions of the world's oceans, which impacts maritime navigation. Methods for generating accurate gridded operational products via the compilation of multiple sources of historical and recent bathymetric collection are of high interest to the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO) [1] and related communities. The general approach to derive gridded product estimates of depth is via surface interpolation [1-4]. Understanding the propagation of *a priori* random error in the source data to the final gridded products is also of interest for providing uncertainty estimates, which can be critical for decision-making. Investigation of this process is the objective of this paper. An ultimate goal is the development of an operational capability for quality control of source data, and quantification/visualization of uncertainty in navigational products.

Our approach is similar to the method proposed in [2], which is based upon Monte Carlo (*MC*) derived uncertainty estimates for the spline-in-tension surface interpolation technique of [3-4]. The Svalbard data set used in [2] is used in this paper; however, we constrain the input to a single bathymetric source to reduce the problem domain in order to facilitate understanding of intra-survey effects. In the absence of control truth data, cross-validation is used as the basis to evaluate the following experimental hypotheses:

H1. The *a priori* uncertainties of random error in survey data described in [2] are reasonable for purposes of *MC* perturbation to estimate (propagated) uncertainty of error in gridded output. Uncertainty of error consists of statistical measures, such as confidence intervals and/or standard deviations.

Good quality *a priori* uncertainties are not necessarily easily derived, particularly for historical data. When in doubt, a conservative approach is to overestimate. An objective of this paper is to determine to what extent cross-validation can provide insight into assessing the quality of *a priori* uncertainties.

H2. Spatially autocorrelated *a priori* random error for intra-survey data has impact on the error estimation (uncertainty estimates) of gridded output.

This hypothesis is an extension of *H1*. The assumption in [2] is that intra-survey *a priori* random errors are uncorrelated. Given the lack of metadata to investigate, much less suggest otherwise, this assumption is difficult to criticize. Nevertheless, it is reasonable to assume some degree of horizontal autocorrelation of error from

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navigation system derived coordinates (e.g., GPS or LORAN). It is further reasonable to assume some degree of horizontal and vertical autocorrelation of error associated with depth measurements. However, estimating realistic spatial correlation functions for this application is certainly non-trivial, if not impractical in some cases. Furthermore, assuming an autocorrelation function is knowable, its effects may be insignificant over the nominal survey point distances considered. In this context, an objective of this paper is to determine to what extent a heuristically derived autocorrelation function leads to measurable effects on estimated uncertainties of gridded output. No assertions are made regarding model validity per se. Rather, our goal is to put forth a rigorous methodology to investigate the effects of autocorrelated errors. Explicit temporal autocorrelation of error, also likely to exist, is not considered since time-stamped data collection information was unavailable.

H3. Survey point density (measured horizontally) is a plausible predictor of uncertainty.

It would seem intuitive to assume that some relationship ought to exist between survey point density and fitting error from surface interpolation, i.e., lower density leading to more uncertainty. This issue was raised in [2]. However, establishing a useful functional relationship is not necessarily straightforward. To that end, an objective of this paper is to investigate use of a ‘density-factor’ metric.

H4. A *MC* approach to error estimation is computationally tenable for “large” areas of interest.

The main limitation of a *MC* method is its high computational requirements. A researcher must generally choose between using a statistically meaningful number of realizations versus data set size to allow for reasonable solution latency. To the extent that *MC* realizations are mutually independent, parallel computation methods can and should be exploited. An objective of this paper is to assess the practicality of data set size versus solution latency when using parallel computation.

H5. Cross-validation for the given data and surface interpolation type is useful to test the preceding hypotheses.

In the absence of controlled data ‘truth’, cross-validation is a viable alternative from which to estimate error. However, its reliability is limited to the accuracy of the input data, since training and test data are drawn from the same population. To reduce this effect, experimentation was constrained to a single survey source that had relatively small *a priori* random errors. An objective of this paper is to determine the value of cross-validation for assessing error estimation in gridded output.

In the remainder of the paper, the Svalbard data set used is described in section 2; the evaluation method used in section 3; the experimental results in section 4; conclusions in section 5; and future work in section 6.

2. The data set

Given the relative scarcity of bathymetric survey data in the Arctic, a primary goal of the IBCAO [5] community is to leverage and combine historical bathymetric data. The general approach is to derive gridded product estimates of depth via surface interpolation [1]. The data set used in this paper was derived from a version of the Svalbard data used in [2], a portion of which is shown in Figure 1. The full data set used in [2] consisted of multiple historical data sources whose estimated inter-survey *a priori* uncertainties of random error varied considerably. In the context of multiple sources, a single source is roughly defined as distinct in terms of equipment and time frame of collection.

The primary objective of [2] was to study the effect of *a priori* random errors in a gridded depth product derived from multiple historical data sources. The goal of this paper is similar, but whose scope is constrained to the two smaller test sets shown in Figure 1. A further constraint is that only a single source (Norwegian single-beam soundings) was considered in this paper. The reason for constraining the data as such was to reduce the problem to fewer variables to facilitate our understanding of the effects of random errors, particularly intra-survey autocorrelation. The Norwegian source was selected in particular due to its broad 3D coverage of the region, widely varying horizontal point densities, and small *a priori* uncertainty of random error, which were “standard deviations” at the 95% confidence interval of 200m (horizontal) and 2% of depth (vertical), which included sound speed corrections [2]. The two test areas were selected to capture varying horizontal densities and depth ranges among the Norwegian data points, while avoiding land masses and large void areas. All bathymetric points were converted to the universal polar stereographic (UPS) projection (true scale at $\sim 81^\circ$ N). Quality control consisted of removing

duplicate entries, and performing a rubber sheet registration to an auxiliary control data source to remove a systematic horizontal bias.

Figure 1. Svalbard study area. Norwegian bathymetric source data (blue dots and tracks); test area 1 (22,333 points, and test area 2 (5,618 points) (red boxes); land (green polygons).

3. Evaluation method

The Monte Carlo approach used in this paper is similar to that as described [2], but with some variation as described in the following subsections: section 3.1 describes the base approach; section 3.2 describes the approach to model spatial autocorrelation; and section 3.3 describes performance metrics.

3.1. Base method

Figure 2 shows the flow diagram of the base approach. The major processing concepts and steps in Figure 2 are underlined in the description that follows.

Cross-validation (CV) belongs to a class of methods that randomly split sample data into training sets for model parameter fitting, and test sets for model performance evaluation (validation). CV can produce parameter estimates that are nearly unbiased [6]. While CV can be computationally demanding, modern computers make it a viable approach. In this paper, *K-fold* cross-validation is used with a 90% | 10% split of training and testing data respectively. Each data split represents a *fold*, which is repeated $K = 10$ times with non-repeating samples such that every sample point can serve as a test point only once. Variations of this approach are described in [6], the merits of which are not investigated in this paper.

The correlate error decision diamond provides the option to spatially autocorrelate Monte Carlo perturbations of XYZ source point (a.k.a., survey or “bathy” sounding) coordinates. For uncorrelated perturbations, perturb XYZ is performed in a straightforward manner. Fast Sequential Simulation (FSS) is a method proposed in [7] to perturb data with spatial autocorrelation, which is described in section 3.2. Since FSS generates perturbations for a regularly space 3D lattice, trilinear interpolation must be performed to extend these perturbations to the actual data points.

Generic Mapping Tools (GMT) is an open source software suite of functions as described in [4], whose development originated in 1990s. The two functions used for this paper are: SURFACE, which is the spline-intension surface interpolation method of [3-4] to create gridded output from bathymetric input; and block median filter (with -Q option), which is to prevent aliasing effects in the gridded output from SURFACE. For all testing purposes the tension parameter was set to 0.35 and the output grid spacing set to 2.5km in x and y dimensions. XYZ perturbations are repeated for $M = 100$ realizations, each run through SURFACE, from which to compute grid stack statistics. A MATLAB script was used to drive the overall process flow, which included calls to GMT functions.

Metrics used for estimation of errors and performance are described in section 3.3.

Figure 2. Base method. Outer cross-validation loop (red), and inner *MC* loop (green).

3.2. Modeling autocorrelation of random errors in support of the *MC* perturbation method: two approaches

The analysis presented in this paper corresponds to two general cases regarding the assumed *a priori* statistical characteristics of the errors associated with 3D “bathy soundings” or source data and the *MC* method: (1) uncorrelated errors, and (2) spatially correlated errors. For both cases, 3D bathy errors are assumed independent between the three components of error, i.e., ϵ_x , ϵ_y , and ϵ_z . Errors are assumed to have a mean value of zero and an *a priori* standard deviation equal to $(200/2.45) = 82$ meters for both ϵ_x and ϵ_y independent of location (homogeneous). The *a priori* standard deviation of ϵ_z is assumed a linear function of depth (nonhomogeneous), and approximately equal to $(2\% / 1.96) = 1\%$ of depth. The values 200 meters and 2% are specified 95% confidence values; the values 2.45 and 1.96 are the appropriate (inverse) conversion factors to standard deviation assuming a Gaussian distribution of errors.

Spatially uncorrelated errors are easily simulated in support of the *MC* method for the generation of grid point standard deviations or predicted accuracy of the grid. Corresponding computations are simple, straightforward, and

the throughput is very fast as the simulation is performed independently per bathy sounding. Spatially correlated errors are not as easily simulated as they are all inter-related. The following describes the technique implemented.

3.2.1. Generation of spatially correlated errors

Fast Sequential Simulation (FSS) was used to generate spatially correlated 3D errors associated with bathy soundings for a given survey. Errors were generated independently for ϵ_x , ϵ_y , and ϵ_z . They were generated sequentially over a 2D lattice for ϵ_x and ϵ_y errors (separately), and were generated sequentially over a 3D lattice for ϵ_z (depth) errors. The former are modeled as homogeneous scalar random fields with horizontal 2D spatial correlation and correspond to the general effects of sounding platform navigation error, and the latter are modeled as a nonhomogeneous scalar random field (standard deviation a function of depth) with 3D spatial correlation and correspond to the general effects of water on acoustic propagation. The corresponding *a priori* standard deviations for the three components of error are as described in the previous paragraphs.

Once the lattices were generated for a particular realization for each of the three scalar random fields, they were interpolated corresponding to each particular sounding of interest and the resultant 3D error added to the sounding. FSS generation corresponding to 2D spatial correlation is described in detail in [7] and was recently generalized by the authors to both 3D and 4D spatial correlations. Figure 3 summarizes the sequential generation of 3D spatially correlated and non-homogeneous z errors (ϵ_z) that was used in various analyses presented in this paper. Generation was performed sequentially starting with the smallest depth plane to the largest depth plane, one lattice point at a time, as outlined in Figure 3.

A priori correlation (ρ) between an arbitrary pair of scalar errors at different lattice points separated by $\Delta l, \Delta k, \Delta j$ grid units is the product of exponential decay in each lattice direction. It is parameterized by the correlation coefficients r, s, t relative to adjacent lattice points in the lattice l, k, j directions, respectively, which are aligned with x, y, z spatial directions, respectively. These correlation coefficients are typically set to a value of 0.95 (or higher) in order to virtually eliminate any adverse smoothing effects associated with subsequent interpolation into the generated (error) lattice. Spacing of the lattice in terms of linear units (δ , meters/grid unit) is determined in each spatial direction by the desired distance constant (D); for example, in the x direction, $\delta_x = -D_x \ln(0.95)$. Thus, the equation for the spatial correlation (coefficient) versus distance between lattice points is:

$$\rho(\Delta j, \Delta k, \Delta l) = r^{\Delta l} s^{\Delta k} t^{\Delta j} = e^{-\delta_x \Delta l / D_x} e^{-\delta_y \Delta k / D_y} e^{-\delta_z \Delta j / D_z}, \quad (1)$$

which is approximately isotropic (in “lattice space”) when $r = s = t$.

The desired *a priori* standard deviation of errors is designated $\sigma_{\epsilon_z}(z)$, an increasing function of depth, as described earlier. Once specified, it is used to “seed” the independent generation of the random error for starting lattice points, and is also used in the formula for the corresponding standard deviation of the driving white noise (σ_u) for the

remaining (correlated) lattice points as presented in Figure 3. However, because of the “inherent lag” between the sequential generation of errors from one depth plane to the next, the actual standard deviation used in this formula (only) is somewhat larger than that specified. Currently, the amount of increase is empirically derived and simple in form, and for the scenarios of interest (operating conditions) in this paper, the formula for the standard deviation of driving what noise is actually:

$$\sigma_u = (1 + 1.7 * \sigma_{\varepsilon z}(z))\sqrt{(1 - r^2)(1 - s^2)(1 - t^2)} \text{ meters} \quad (2)$$

This corresponding increase is larger for the scenarios of interest in this paper than for other possible scenarios (operating conditions), as the relative range of values for the specified $\sigma_{\varepsilon z}(z)$ is large (0 to 35 meters, or 0:35) corresponding to depths ranging from 0 to 3.5 km, as opposed to a smaller relative range (20 to 50 meters, or 20:50) for depths ranging from 2 km to 5 km, for example. However, simulated errors for the scenarios of interest were verified as approximately consistent with both the specified spatial correlation (D_x, D_y, D_z) and specified variance ($\sigma_{\varepsilon z}^2(z)$). And finally, and as an aside, if $\sigma_{\varepsilon z}(z)$ is not a function of depth, i.e., constant and the random field homogeneous, it is used directly in Equation (2), i.e., $(1 + 1.7 * \sigma_{\varepsilon z}(z)) \rightarrow \sigma_{\varepsilon z}$, and the sample statistics of the simulated errors will match the desired *a priori* statistics “exactly”, or more correctly, within the appropriate sampling error or statistical significance. (Note: the symbol $\sigma_{\varepsilon z}(z)$ used in the above description of FSS represents a different quantity than does the symbol $\sigma_{\varepsilon z}$ in the upcoming Section 3.3 on performance metrics.)

3.2.2. Generation speed for spatially correlated errors using FSS 10⁸

FSS is fast as shown in Figure 4, with results based on a typical notebook computer (single processor) with 8 GB ram. Time increases linearly with number of lattice points. FSS is shown superior in terms of speed relative to more traditional methods in [7]. Note that in our bathy application, the size of the lattice (number of generated spatially correlated errors for a given error type and given realization) is determined by the desired volume of coverage and the linear grid spacing. 10⁷

Figure 4. Number of lattice points (spatially correlated scalar errors) (y-axis) vs. FSS generation time for 2D (blue), 3D (magenta), and 4D (red) spatial correlation (x-axis). 10⁶

3.2.3 Sources and degree of spatial correlations

As mentioned previously, in the various performance studies of Section 4 involving spatial correlation, horizontal errors ($\varepsilon x, \varepsilon y$) are modelled as 2D spatially (horizontally) correlated with constant standard deviations, and depth errors (εz) are modelled as 3D spatially correlated with standard deviation increasing with depth. The degree of horizontal correlation of horizontal errors is related to platform navigation errors and corresponding distance constants. The latter are related to correlation time constants of the navigation source signals (e.g., LORAN, Transit, GPS, etc.) and the velocity of the platform. The effect of platform position errors on bathy sounding horizontal errors is essentially independent of depth; hence the use of 2D spatial correlation instead of 3D. The degree of 3D spatial correlation of depth errors is related to acoustic propagation effects through water; dependent on currents, salinity, temperature, etc., and the accuracy of corresponding correction processes. The 3D distance constants are essentially empirically derived and dependent of the general location of the soundings. In the spatial correlation studies presented in Section 4, all distance constants corresponding to both horizontal and depth errors are documented and were set to assumed reasonably large values ($D_x = D_y = 30 \text{ km}$, $D_z = 3 \text{ km}$) in order to “bound” any effects due to spatial correlation (as compared to the effects of uncorrelated errors). The specified values of $D_x = D_y = 30 \text{ km}$ for horizontal errors are more appropriate to historical bathy soundings performed years ago without the benefit of GPS. And, admittedly, the values for $D_x, D_y,$ and D_z for depth errors are somewhat of a “guestimate”. Detailed future analyses are required in order to determine more appropriate values parameterized by bathy sounding source and general location.

3.3. Statistical metrics proposed for general performance assessment

Various performance metrics are required in order to assess the performance of the *MC* perturbation method for the generation of grid standard deviation of error or predicted accuracy, the utility and consequences of K-fold cross-validation, the reliability of the *a priori* uncertainties for bathy sounding errors, the effects of the distribution of bathy soundings, etc.

The primary metric for performance assessment is “grid total error” or ϵZ , computed as the (depth) difference of a sounding held out of the grid (spline fit) generation process with its interpolated counterpart from the generated grid. However, there are a number of important related metrics used in the various analyses that follow, including “grid error sigma” or $\sigma_{\epsilon grid}$, “normalized error” or $\epsilon Z/\sigma_{\epsilon Z}$, and “density-factor” or fd . Strictly speaking, each of these metrics is associated with a specific point or grid cell, but all also have corresponding statistical summaries. The following provides more detailed definitions and comments:

3.3.1. **“Grid total error” ϵZ** is defined as follows:

$$\epsilon Z = z_{grid} - z_{bathy}, \quad (3)$$

where z_{grid} is the value of depth interpolated from a grid cell and corresponding to the location of z_{bathy} , a bathy sounding left out of the current cross-validation fold during Monte-Carlo generation of grid standard deviations. z_{bathy} is an estimate of the (unknown) truth or z_{true} . The grid total error ϵZ includes: (1) grid error ϵZ_{grid} , which is grid (spline fit) error at the surrounding grid points relative to true depth propagated via bilinear interpolation to the bathy sounding location, (2) corresponding grid interpolation error ϵZ_{int} , particularly that associated with abrupt changes in the ocean floor, and (3) the error ϵZ_{bathy} in the individual bathy sounding representing true depth. The interpolation error ϵZ_{int} corresponds to the difference in the (unknown) true ocean floor relative to the surface defined by bilinear interpolation of assumed error-free grid points. (Note: the symbol ϵZ represents “grid total error” as above, unless specifically prefaced by “depth error”, in which it corresponds to a perturbation or error as described in Section 3.2.1.)

3.3.2. **“Grid error sigma” $\sigma_{\epsilon grid}$** is the standard deviation of the grid error ϵZ_{grid} . It is approximated as the bilinear interpolation of the unique $\sigma_{\epsilon grid}$ assigned to each of the four surrounding grid points based on the Monte-Carlo simulation of sounding errors or perturbations (*MC* method) as describe in [2]. (Note: the standard error of the estimate of standard deviation (grid error sigma) was not computed explicitly in our analysis.)

3.3.3. **“Normalized error” $\epsilon Z/\sigma_{\epsilon Z}$** is defined as grid total error ϵZ divided by its *a priori* standard deviation $\sigma_{\epsilon Z}$ (note: this is not grid error ϵZ_{grid} divided by its standard deviation, grid error sigma $\sigma_{\epsilon grid}$):

$$\epsilon Z/\sigma_{\epsilon Z} = (z_{grid} - z_{bathy}) / (\sigma_{\epsilon grid}^2 + \sigma_{\epsilon bathy}^2 - 2\rho\sigma_{\epsilon grid}\sigma_{\epsilon bathy} + \sigma_{\epsilon int}^2)^{1/2}, \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{\epsilon grid}$ is the standard deviation of grid error ϵZ_{grid} , $\sigma_{\epsilon bathy}$ is the *a priori* standard deviation of the error ϵZ_{bathy} , ρ is the *a priori* correlation coefficient between the grid and bathy sounding errors, ϵZ_{grid} and ϵZ_{bathy} , and $\sigma_{\epsilon int}$ is the *a priori* standard deviation of (uncorrelated) interpolation error.

Note that in Equation (4), the numerator can also be written as Equation (5) and the denominator is defined as Equation (6):

$$\epsilon Z = (z_{grid} - z_{bathy}) = (z_{true} + \epsilon Z_{grid} + \epsilon Z_{int}) - (z_{true} + \epsilon Z_{bathy}) = (\epsilon Z_{grid} + \epsilon Z_{int} - \epsilon Z_{bathy}), \quad (5)$$

$$\left(E \left\{ (\epsilon Z_{grid} + \epsilon Z_{int} - \epsilon Z_{bathy})^2 \right\} \right)^{1/2} = (\sigma_{\epsilon grid}^2 + \sigma_{\epsilon bathy}^2 - 2\rho\sigma_{\epsilon grid}\sigma_{\epsilon bathy} + \sigma_{\epsilon int}^2)^{1/2}, \quad (6)$$

where E is the expected value operator and errors are assumed to have a mean value of zero. Further note, for $\sigma_{\epsilon bathy}$ only, its value directly reflects the uncertainty of bathy sounding depth, i.e., any effects due to horizontal error via ocean floor slope are assumed negligible for the current analysis of the scenarios of interest. Also, the

appropriate value and methodology to compute the standard deviation of interpolation error, σ_{eint} , requires investigation, and for the analysis presented in this paper, σ_{eint} is simply assumed equal to zero. That is, the true surface of the ocean floor is assumed exactly representable as a surface generated from an error-free bilinear interpolation, i.e., reasonably “smooth”. We plan to modify this assumption appropriately in future analysis.

If bathy sounding errors are assumed and modelled as uncorrelated, the correlation between the grid error and the error in a bathymetric sounding representing truth (and not affecting the grid) are also uncorrelated, i.e., $\rho = 0$. On the other hand, if bathy sounding errors are assumed and modelled as spatially correlated, $\rho \neq 0$, since the errors in bathy soundings used to generate the grid are positively correlated with the error in the bathy sounding representing “truth”. A reasonable estimate for the range of ρ is $0 \leq \rho < 0.7$; however, the appropriate value is point specific, dependent on bathy sounding density in the region, and the shape of the local spline. We do not know the appropriate value for ρ at this time; hence, the value was set to zero, i.e., $\rho = 0$. This crude estimate is a consequence of using cross-validation, as opposed to independent truth, where we know that ρ is indeed equal to zero.

Thus, regardless if bathy sounding errors are modelled as correlated or spatially correlated, Equation (4) reduces to:

$$\varepsilon Z / \sigma_{\varepsilon Z} = (z_{\text{grid}} - z_{\text{bathy}}) / (\sigma_{\varepsilon \text{grid}}^2 + \sigma_{\varepsilon \text{bathy}}^2 + \sigma_{\varepsilon \text{int}}^2)^{1/2}, \text{ since } \rho \text{ is assumed equal to zero.} \quad (7)$$

Consequently, for bathy sounding errors modelled as uncorrelated and bathy sounding errors modelled as spatially correlated, their corresponding values of normalized error at a specific point differ only due to differences in their corresponding values of grid error sigma.

Note also that, in Equation (4) for normalized error, it would be preferable that the value for $\sigma_{\varepsilon \text{bathy}}$ (standard deviation of “truth” error) be reliably known and negligible, in addition to the value of ρ reliably known and equal to zero, whether (intra-survey) bathy sounding errors are modeled as uncorrelated or spatially correlated. These attributes enable an accurate and more direct assessment of the quantities of interest: grid error and its standard deviation. However, this will only occur if “truth” corresponds to a (relatively) accurate and independent survey, not K-fold cross-validation. And, of course, this may not be possible. However, regardless this caveat, the normalized error (metric) $\varepsilon Z / \sigma_{\varepsilon Z}$ is an important indicator of the validity of the grid error sigma (predicted accuracy) and its underlying Monte-Carlo generation method. The validity of the latter depends on reliable *a priori* uncertainties for the bathy sounding errors, and “proper” implementation of grid generation per se, which relies on appropriate sounding density and compatible grid cell spacing. If errors are approximately Gaussian distributed, we expect approximately 68%, 95%, and 99% of the normalized errors to be within +/- 1, +/- 2, and +/- 3, respectively.

3.3.4. **Density-factor fd** is a scalar metric indicating the density of the soundings used to generate the grid relative to a particular grid cell. If the density-factor is too small (too few relevant soundings), the corresponding grid was not generated properly near the grid cell, and correspondingly, grid error sigma is probably unreliable. The density-factor is a measure of sounding density and its spatial symmetry relative to a grid cell. It is computed over a 7x7 cell grid centered at the grid cell of interest. Surrounding grid cells closest to the center have more weight (score) than those further away, with extra weight given if they surround the center cell in a (near) symmetric manner. The value of fd ranges between a value of 0 to 10, with $fd \approx \geq 6.5$ considered “good”.

4. Results

This section of the paper presents results corresponding to the cross-validation of error and use of the *MC* method for estimating corresponding grid error sigma (standard deviation or predicted accuracy) for grids generated using spline-in-tension and available bathy soundings over the areas of interest. Results are primarily presented as plots/figures of the various performance metrics described previously in Section 3.3. Test areas 1 and 2 are addressed separately in sections 4.1 and 4.2 respectively.

4.1. Test Area-1

The extent of Test Area-1 is shown in Figure 1 relative to the Svalbard study area. It consists of 22,333 survey or bathy sounding points (not grid points) over a depth range of 3-564m. The nearest horizontal neighbor RMS

distance between survey points was computed at 1,896m. In the sub sections that follow, issues of error and normalized error estimation, density and parametric effects are addressed.

4.1.1. Error estimation

Simulated perturbations or errors in support of the *MC* method were either uncorrelated or autocorrelated (spatially correlated). The corresponding algorithm parameters used in FSS for the latter and 3D spatial correlation of depth error ϵ_z were: $[D_x, D_y, D_z] = [30,000 \ 30,000 \ 3,000]\text{m}$; $[r_x, r_y, r_z] = [0.95 \ 0.95 \ 0.95]$; and where lattice spacing is,

$$[\delta_x, \delta_y, \delta_z] = \text{per_element_product}\{-\ln([r_x, r_y, r_z]), [D_x, D_y, D_z]\} = [1,538.8, 1,538.8, 153.9]\text{m} \quad (8)$$

For 2D spatial correlation of horizontal errors, the same horizontal distance constants were used; hence, the same horizontal spacing. The *a priori* standard deviations for ϵ_x and ϵ_y were both 82 meters, and for ϵ_z , 1% of depth.

Figure 5 presents the corresponding spline fit (grid), grid total errors ϵ_z (cross-validation errors), grid error sigmas $\sigma_{\epsilon_{grid}}$ (at the grid points) via the *MC* method for one-fold of the cross-validation of errors process. Note that there are non-trivial differences in grid error sigma depending on the assumed type of correlation used in the *MC* method. In general, in dense sounding areas, grid error sigma is smaller when bathy sounding errors are modelled as uncorrelated than for when errors are modelled as spatially correlated, probably due to the former's "averaging" of independent (uncorrelated) errors across numerous bathy soundings generating the corresponding grid cell. In non-dense areas, the reverse is true. Of course, a complicating and somewhat obfuscating factor is that areas with dense soundings usually correspond to shallow water, and non-dense areas to deeper water.

4.1.2. Normalized error estimation

Figure 6 presents the corresponding normalized error metric $\epsilon_z/\sigma_{\epsilon_z}$ (grid total error divided by its *a priori* standard deviation) across Area-1 assuming uncorrelated errors (left) and spatially correlated errors (right), and Figure 7 their corresponding histograms. Note that the latter appear roughly Gaussian distributed, but with (symmetric) confidence intervals that exceed their theoretical values of 1, 2, and 3, corresponding to 68%, 95%, and 99%, respectively, by about a factor of about 2x or 3x. Thus, there is some sort of "mis-modelling" going on, probably a combination of incorrect (too small) *a priori* uncertainties for bathy sounding errors, subareas of inadequate density (see corresponding density-factor metric plots in Section 4.1.3), sounding blunders, and possibly excessive interpolation error.

The sample mean of normalized error is negligible for both bathy sounding errors modelled as uncorrelated and modelled as spatially correlated. Also, there is little difference in their overall histograms (Figure 7). Of course, for errors modelled as spatially correlated, the value for ρ in the formula for normalized errors is not well-known, and assumed equal to zero per the discussion of Section 3.3.3. When it was set to $\rho = 0.5$, the corresponding histogram retained the same symmetric shape about zero, but spread out; for example, the 68% confidence interval increased from a value of 2.04 to 2.8, i.e., got "worse".

Finally, based on the histograms of normalized error, more applicable distributions than the Gaussian distribution, and their relationship to confidence intervals, are to be explored. One such candidate is a double exponential or Laplacian distribution. Preliminary analysis indicates that its probability distribution function fits both histograms reasonably well, assuming a standard deviation of approximately 2.5, instead of the value 1.0 expected assuming no mis-modelling.

Figure 5. (upper left) mean estimates of depth (z) for fold (k=10); (upper right) cross-validation error of depth (z) for all folds; (lower left) standard deviation of grid error (grid error sigma) for fold (k=10) from uncorrelated perturbations; (lower right) standard deviation for fold (k=10) from autocorrelated (spatially correlated) perturbations in x, y, z.

Figure 6. Normalized error estimation from cross-validation over all folds. (left) uncorrelated perturbations; (right) spatially autocorrelated perturbations in x, y, z.

Figure 7. Histograms of normalized error for Area-1; uncorrelated errors or perturbation (left) and spatially correlated (right) used in the corresponding *MC* method; x-axis is normalized Z error, which is unit-less.

4.1.3. Point density effects

As discussed in the previous section, the normalized errors of the surface estimation provide a good metric determining the quality of the surface. There are, however, some outliers that occur in the data when the normalized errors are extremely high. It is our opinion that using the density-factor metric can aid in determining areas where the normalized errors will be large. Figure 8 (left) describes the density-factor metric for Area-1, where the highly dense areas are represented in red and the sparse areas are represented in blue. Using the results of all ten folds of the Monte Carlo simulations, the figures to the right were generated for the test points. The 68th percentile, 95th percentile and the RMS of the normalized error is plotted against the density-factor metric.

Figure 8. Density-factor metric plot (left); density-factor relationship with uncorrelated normalized error (top right); and autocorrelated normalized error (bottom right).

There are some cases (sub-areas) where this relationship does not perform as expected, indicating *a priori* mis-modelling other than insufficient bathy sounding point density to properly generate the grid and corresponding grid error standard deviations. Figure 9 is relative to a sub-area of Area-1, where the point density metric is very high. There are some crossing tracks within the data that tend to have a higher normalized error even in areas where the density-factor metric is high. Our theory is these crossing tracks were collected at a different time than the circular tracks. The data used in this study does not have any temporal information in regards to when the survey data was collected. This could explain the higher normalized errors for these crossing tracks, which may have been collected at a different time as the circular tracks - respective *a priori* uncertainties inconsistent or wrong for the crossing and/or circular tracks.

Figure 9. Density-factor (left) versus uncorrelated normalized error (right). Note high transect normalized errors relative to density-factor; horizontal units are meters.

4.1.4. Other parametric effects

Other parametric effects are presented in Figure 10. As can be seen on the left, assessed grid total error (cross-validation error) and corresponding computation time both appear reasonable for cross-validation based on $K = 10$ folds. As can be seen on the right, spline grid spacing at 2.5 km x 2.5 km appears reasonable in terms of corresponding grid total error for the available bathy soundings over the area. However, unstable behavior can be observed from the spline-in-tension algorithm at as spacing decreases. We speculate that this may be an artefact of insufficient point sample density, but only note the effects here.

Figure 10. (left) cross-validation error as a function of folds (K) (blue), and CPU time (green); (right) cross-validation error as a function of grid spacing for 1000m to 3000m for GMT's spline-in-tension.

4.2. Test Area-2

The extent of Test Area-2 is shown in Figure 1 relative to the Svalbard study area. It consists of 5,618 survey points over a depth range of 66 - 3,487m. The nearest horizontal neighbor RMS distance between survey points is 1,452m. In the sub sections that follow, issues of error and normalized error estimation, and density effects are addressed.

4.2.1. Error estimation

Figure 11 presents the corresponding spline fit (grid), grid total errors ε_z (cross-validation errors), grid error sigmas $\sigma_{\varepsilon_{grid}}$ (at the grid points) via the *MC* method for one-fold of the cross-validation of errors process. Again, as for Area-1, there are non-trivial differences in grid error sigma (predicted accuracy) depending on the assumed type of correlation used in the *MC* method. However, for Area-2, spatially correlated errors generally yield larger grid error sigma in the less-dense areas and deeper water, the latter significantly deeper than for Area-1. (*A priori* statistics for the errors or perturbations were the same as for Area-1, previously described in Section 4.1.1.)

Figure 11. Area 2 (upper left) mean estimates of depth (z) for a single fold ($k=10$); (upper right) cross-validation error of depth (z) for all folds; (lower left) standard deviation of grid error (grid error sigma) for a single fold ($k=10$) from uncorrelated perturbations; (lower right) standard deviation for a single fold ($k=10$) from autocorrelated perturbations in x, y, z .

4.2.2. Normalized error estimation

Figure 12 presents the corresponding normalized error metric $\varepsilon_z/\sigma_{\varepsilon_z}$ (grid total error divided by its *a priori* standard deviation) across Area-2 assuming uncorrelated errors (top) and spatially correlated errors (bottom), and Figure 13 their corresponding histograms. Note that the latter appear only somewhat Gaussian distributed, and have (symmetric) confidence intervals that exceed their theoretical values of 1, 2, and 3, corresponding to 68%, 95%, and 99%, respectively. In particular, by about a factor of 2x or 3x, for both uncorrelated and spatially correlated errors. Again, there is some sort of “mis-modelling” going on as described earlier for Area-1. (Also, $\rho = 0$ for spatially correlated errors – see the relevant discussion in Sections 4.1.2)

Figure 12. Area-2 normalized error estimation from cross-validation over all folds. (top) uncorrelated perturbations; (bottom) spatially autocorrelated perturbations in x,y,z.

Figure 13. Histograms of normalized error for Area-2; uncorrelated errors or perturbation (left) and spatially correlated (right) used in the corresponding MC method.

In general, for both Area-1 and Area-2, future analyses should also compute histograms of normalized error that include constraints based on specified ranges for corresponding values of the density-factor metric.

4.2.3. Point density effects

The relationship between the density-factor metric and normalized error appears weaker for Area-2 than for Area-1 as illustrated in Figure 14. We believe the reason for this is probably due to the smaller area, which produces a smaller sample size. Also, Area-2 contains a more homogeneous density of points, where Area-1 has sparse areas as well as dense areas of soundings. The relationship between the normalized error and the density-factor metric should remain an item for study, where larger datasets with varying density should be included.

Figure 14. Density-factor metric plot and relationships with normalized error for Area-2. (left) uncorrelated; (right) correlated.

4.3. Computational speed assessment

The creation of cross validation statistics is relatively lengthy to compute. In our simulations, we performed 100 Monte Carlo trials for each of the 10 folds, which is 1000 Monte Carlo trials for the area of interest. The time needed to perform these computations could be costly; however, our simulation proved otherwise. The initial simulation performed used the GMT Surface program to perform the spline fit directly in a command line interface.

This did take some time to perform and it was noted only one processor was being used. We then used the source code that accompanied GMT Surface and rewrote it to take advantage of all processors available on a computer. Another advantage of recoding the software allows the data to be stored in memory for all the trials, which minimizes reading and writing to the disk. The recoding of the software allowed us to have a much better understanding of what is being performed in GMT Surface. For example, [2] advocates using a block median filter on the survey data prior to being run in GMT Surface to minimize aliasing. The resulting data set from the block median filter gives at most one point (bathy sounding) per grid cell. Therefore, the maximum number of points to be processed in an area is equal to the total number of grid points or cells.

The two test areas were used in performing the timing simulations for the uncorrelated and correlated cases. The time needed for the 10 folds, each with 100 *MC* realizations, was measured along with the total number of grid points representing the surface of the ocean floor (i.e., the area of the estimated surface). Assuming the processing time is approximately linear with respect to area, the processing time for the entire Svalbard area can be extrapolated from the timing trials of Area-1 and Area-2.

Table 1. Timing results for Area-1 and Area-2 with extrapolated times (*) for the uncorrelated and autocorrelated Svalbard area.

	Area-1	Area-2	Svalbard
Uncorrelated time (s)	13.9	0.5	80.2*
Autocorrelated time (s)	21.6	5.7	97.7*
Grid Points	49020	5671	263457
Area (km²)	306375	35444	1646606

Table 1 shows the processing time for computing surfaces, corresponding grid error sigma's via the *MC* method, and cross-validation as described earlier, for the various areas. The target machine we used is a 32-core machine running at 2.4 GHz with 32 GB of RAM. Parallel processing allows for simultaneous processing of multiple Monte Carlo realizations.

The above timing estimates correspond to the use of one survey (data source) providing bathy soundings versus *N* surveys. We expect processing times to increase as an approximate direct multiple of *N* when additional surveys are processed simultaneously.

In addition, when errors are modelled as spatially correlated, processing times are a function of the degree of *a priori* spatial correlation (distance constants) specified. The values of the distance constants in the runs to-date and applicable to Table 1 are documented in Section 3.2.3. If any of these distance constants decreases, the FSS lattice grid densifies, and correspondingly FSS processing time increases. For example, if both the *x* and the *y* spatial direction distance constants, for both horizontal and depth errors, decrease from 30,000 to 10,000 meters, a factor of 3x each, the number of lattice points for an area of interest will increase by 9x, as will FSS processing time. (The vast majority of this increase is due to depth errors, as they are simulated with a 3D lattice, as opposed to horizontal errors, which are simulated with a 2D lattice.) However, total processing involves more processes than FSS alone; hence, for Area-1, total (autocorrelated) time increases from 21.6 to 117.6 seconds, a factor of approximately 5x. Further examples involving even more reduction of the distance constants, and hence densification of the FSS lattice, are planned. It is worth pointing out that more extreme densification of the lattice will probably require its "smart buffering" and output to general memory during its generation, as well as its subsequent retrieval on a sub-region basis, in order to avoid internal memory (RAM) issues.

The upshot is that total processing time for the entire Svalbard area takes approximately a few minutes, assuming the simultaneous processing of one or two surveys, and use of similar computing architecture. This also assumes that errors are either modelled as uncorrelated, or modelled as spatially correlated errors with distance constants (degree of spatial correlation) as specified in Section 3.2.3. Finally, Table 1 corresponds to total processing time for cross-validation and the *MC* method. If cross-validation is not included explicitly in an operational concept for gridded product generation, times in Table 1 are reduced by approximately 10x; for example, reduced to 8 and 10 seconds for uncorrelated and spatially correlated (autocorrelated) errors, respectively, for the entire Svalbard area.

5. Observations

Based on the analysis presented in Section 4, we believe the following observations are applicable:

The grid normalized error metric appears a reasonable measure of the reliability of grid error sigma (predicted accuracy or uncertainty) generated via the *MC* method, particularly when evaluated in conjunction with the proposed grid density-factor metric. However, more analysis needs to be done in this area, with more statistical significance and consideration regarding the correlation of the grid density-factor metric with other parameters, such as sounding depth. For the data analyzed, the distribution of the grid normalized error metric indicates normalized errors that appear roughly Gaussian distributed, but with magnitude 2-3 times greater than if all assumptions were correct; thus, for example, the *a priori* uncertainties for bathy sounding random errors may be too optimistic. Another possible contributor may be non-trivial interpolation error per the discussion of Section 3.3.3, i.e., σ_{int} significantly greater than zero. In addition, the distribution tails appeared excessively long, which may be due to possible bathy sounding blunders, per the discussion of Section 4.1.3.

The generation of spatially correlated errors in the *MC* method is feasible. For the scenarios analyzed, they did affect grid error sigma (predicted accuracy) relative to those values computed assuming uncorrelated errors. However, results for normalized error differed little between the two methods.

Physically, it makes sense that errors are spatially correlated. However, more appropriate values for distance constants (amount of correlation) associated with spatially correlated errors are needed. Also, the uncertainty in the value of ρ used in the Equation (4) for normalized error can be circumvented by using independent and accurate truth instead of truth based on cross-validation. If independent and accurate truth is not available, analysis based on the evaluation of another source(s) of data while using the more accurate Norwegian single-beam sounding source as independent “truth” may be useful.

Cross-validation, including the *MC* method, is fast for large areas of interest, both for errors modelled as uncorrelated and spatially correlated. Estimated processing times for the entire Svalbard area and for both types of correlation is only on the order of a few minutes, assuming the use of one or two surveys (data sources) and a commercially available multi-core computer system. However, estimated processing time corresponding to spatially correlated errors will increase if assumed *a priori* distance constants decrease as discussed in Section 4.3.

Based upon the above observations, a candidate set of product contents and corresponding “operations” concept for product generation are as follows. A product includes: (1) a grid of ocean floor depths, (2) corresponding grid error sigma’s representing their uncertainty or predicted accuracy, and (3) reliability “flags” for the latter. The specific form/content of the reliability “flags” is to-be-determined; however, they are generated from a combination of the normalized error and density-factor metrics. The use of normalized error is either explicit, if cross-validation is performed, or implicit, if performed previously and applied as a Bayesian process through the density-factor metric. Also, a possible replacement for grid error sigma is some form of confidence interval. Additional product contents under consideration include that necessary to predict the accuracy of interpolated grid values, as opposed to predicated accuracy at the grid points alone.

In terms of the operations concept per se, after the initial product is generated, including cross-validation, it is then subject to QC for those grid points that either have corresponding large normalized errors or large grid error sigma, and “good” density-metric values, indicating unanticipated large errors or problems. After QC is performed, the final product is generated using all of the remaining/modified data and without cross-validation. There can still be sub-regions within the product with large (unknown) errors and/or unreliable grid error sigma’s – these are “indicated” to the down-stream user by large grid error sigma’s and/or “poor” reliability flag values.

6. Conclusions

We conclude with responses R1-R5 to the specific hypotheses H1-H5 of Section 1.

R1: While the *a priori* uncertainties for source data (bathy sounding) errors appear reasonable in general, they do appear optimistic (too small) for vertical error by a factor of approximately 2x, when results are generalized across Area-1 and Area-2. This conclusion is based on large normalized errors. However, further analysis is needed, as

well as classification of results by corresponding bathy sounding density and depth. Results will also be clearer when interpolation error is better known (modelled), and truth is available that is both accurate and independent of the bathy soundings.

R2: We believe that both horizontal and depth source data errors are spatially correlated; however, the degree of spatial correlation is source data dependent, and not known at this time. Nonetheless, one of the objectives of this paper was to measure the effects of a heuristically derived spatial correlation model. These effects were reasonably significant for propagated uncertainty (grid error sigma), but not for normalized errors. The latter conclusion may change if independent and accurate truth is available and used, and correspondingly, the “fidelity” of normalized errors increases. It may also change if source data other than the Norwegian single-beam sounding data is used. In summary, we do conclude that spatially correlated errors do affect grid predicted accuracy; however, not so much as to replace the simplifying assumption of uncorrelated errors at this time.

R3: While a relationship between the depth-factor metric and normalized error was demonstrated to some extent, additional factors, e.g. depth, are likely needed to infer a stronger relationship.

R4: The timing results from Table 1 indicate that the *MC* method used in this paper (i.e., 100 simulations across 10 cross-validation folds) should be computationally feasible for much larger areas than those tested. Furthermore, the technique shown to include spatial correlation was also computationally feasible.

R5: Our conclusion is that cross-validation is a viable technique for estimating model (spline) fitting errors to the extent that *a priori* uncertainties for test data remain ‘within reason’, which was so stipulated at the start of the experiment. K-fold cross-validation was then used to reveal departures of the surface spline relative to “truth” and the grid’s predicted error (uncertainty) via the normalized error metric. A complicating factor with this method is the (unknown) degree of correlation (ρ) of the fit (grid) errors with the errors in bathy soundings held out of the fit in order to act as “truth”. The availability of controlled and accurate truth data removes this and other complicating factors, and could be used to more definitively evaluate the usefulness of cross-validation.

6. Future work

The following list suggests future directions with the method proposed in this paper:

- Develop an operational concept from which to perform data QC, and visual aids for expressing uncertainty.
- Evaluate method with more reliable truth. In lieu of, or in conjunction with, reliable truth-- simulate a realistic sea floor to assume perfect truth for complementary model insights.
- Extend method to compilations of heterogeneous data sets.
- Assess significance of spatial autocorrelation with multi-beam data.
- Sensitivity analysis to compare performance among surface interpolation methods, e.g., Kriging.

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